

Canvas Quick Start Guide

Suggestions and tips for setting up your Canvas account and navigating your Canvas courses

Created by staff at the Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement (CSCCE)

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About the guide

Welcome to the CSCCE Canvas Learning Management System (Canvas LMS) – a place for learners enrolled in CSCCE trainings to access course materials and submit assignments.

This guide contains some quick tips to help you to configure and use Canvas in a way that works best for you. They are organized into four key areas that describe:

1. Canvas account creation
2. Navigation
3. Profile configuration and account settings
4. Managing notifications

Any questions? Email: tech.help@cscce.org

Note: *These instructions are created for the desktop browser version of Canvas. Access to CSCCE Courses through the Canvas app and mobile browser are not supported at this time.*

Acknowledgements

CSCCE uses the CREDiT contributor roles taxonomy to show how the authors listed contributed to the creation of this guide:

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Citing and reusing this guide

CITATION AND REUSE

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Cite as: Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement. (2023) Canvas Quick Start Guide: Suggestions and tips for setting up your Canvas account and navigating your Canvas courses. Martinic, Pratt, and Woodley doi: [10.5281/zenodo.10287313](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10287313)

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Last updated December 2023

1. Canvas account creation

You will need a Google Account to log into CSCCE’s Canvas. If you do not have one, you can [create a Google Account](#) using any email address or create a new Gmail address. Read more about [Google’s third-party login service here](#).

- Go to <https://cscce.instructure.com> to and choose “[G] Login with Google” to log in with your Google Account email address and password on the “Sign-in to continue to Canvas” page.
 - Please note the data sharing that you agree to by clicking Next. We’ve configured CSCCE Canvas to only use your name and email address to create your Canvas account.
- Read and agree to the Canvas Acceptable User Policy, click Submit.
- Congratulations! Your Canvas user account is created and you will be taken to the Dashboard. You will now always use the “[G] Login with Google” button to sign into Canvas.

2. Navigation

A. GLOBAL NAVIGATION

The Global Navigation Menu for Canvas is the vertical bar on the far left of any Canvas page. In the CSCCE Canvas, this menu includes Account, Dashboard, Courses, Calendar, Inbox, History, and Help.

- **Account** - From here you can update your notification preferences, Profile and other settings. You can also go here to log out of Canvas.
- **Dashboard** - This is the landing page that you'll see when you log into Canvas. It shows your courses, notifications, and recent activity. The default view shows a card for each course you are enrolled in - click a card to go to the home page for that course. (See the [How do I use the Dashboard as a student? Canvas guide](#) for additional information.)
- **Courses** - Clicking this displays a pop-up menu with the courses in which you're enrolled.
- **Calendar** - Opens the calendar page to show course due dates. You can also access the Calendar feed from here (bottom right of the Calendar page) and import it into your own calendar tool.
- **Inbox** - Opens the Canvas direct message tool. *Note: we will NOT use this tool for CSCCE courses. We will be using Slack to communicate between sessions, supplemented with some notifications from Canvas.*
- **History** - Displays a list of pages you've recently visited.
- **Help** - Displays a list of ways to get help, including how to email us and Search the Canvas Guides.

See the [How do I use the Global Navigation Menu as a student? Canvas guide](#) for additional information

B. COURSE NAVIGATION

The course menu on the left side of the Home page of a course includes Home, Announcements (visible after an announcement is sent), Assignments, Submissions (in some courses), and People.

- **Home** - A summary of the course, course schedule, and useful links
- **Announcements** - Revisit all prior announcements from the course
- **Assignments** - A list of all course assignments with open and due dates
- **Submissions** - if your course has graded work, you can find grades here
- **People** - A list of all the learners and CSCCE staff in the course

C. SUBMITTING ASSIGNMENTS

In some courses, you will be asked to upload a file, respond to a reflection prompt, or take a quiz.

To upload a file:

- Click the "Start Assignment" button at the top right corner of the page
- Click "Upload File" then browse/choose your file from your computer
- Then, click "Submit Assignment"

File Upload

Upload a file, or choose a file you've already uploaded.

Upload File Use Webcam

+ Add Another File

[Click here to find a file you've already uploaded](#)

Comments...

Cancel Submit Assignment

To respond to a reflection prompt:

- Click the "Start Assignment" button at the top right corner of the page
- Type in the Text Entry box that appears at the bottom of the page (shown right)
- Click "Submit Assignment"

Text Entry

Copy and paste or type your submission right here.

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0 words

Cancel Submit Assignment

To take a quiz:

- Click the "Take the Quiz" button
- Answer the questions (they auto-save!)
- Click "Submit Quiz" when you are finished

Week 1 homework recap quiz

Due Oct 16 at 10am Points 4 Questions 4
Available after Oct 12 at 1:30pm Time Limit None
Allowed Attempts Unlimited

Instructions

Lesson *pre-work*

Home Week 1 Week 2 Week 3 Week 4 Week 5 Week 6

Week 1: Social roles of community-engaged content recap quiz

We've created a quiz to affirm what you've learned about the social roles of community-engaged content.

How to complete the quiz:

- Click the "Take the Quiz" button below
- Answer the questions (they auto-save!)
- Click "Submit Quiz"
- Your quiz page will refresh and show your answers and the correct answers
- (optional) You can click the "Take the Quiz Again" button if you like!
- Extra help: Please contact tech.help@cscce.org

Take the Quiz

If you have any problems completing assignments, email tech.help@cscce.org.

3. Profile configuration and account settings

A. PROFILE CONFIGURATION

Your profile will be visible to all CSCCE staff and other learners in the courses in which you're enrolled. To make changes to your profile:

- Select "Account" at the top of the global navigation
- Select "Profile" from the pop up
- Then, select "Edit Profile"

Please customize the following fields:

- **Your profile photo** - choose a picture that you're comfortable with so that others can recognize your contributions more easily.
 - Hover over the gray "person" icon and a pencil icon will appear. Click the icon and, in the pop-up, choose "Upload a Picture" or "Take a Picture".
 - To upload a picture, click "choose a picture" under the gray picture icon to display a dialog box and select a file from your computer.
 - To take a picture, allow Canvas to access your webcam and then click "Take a Picture" below the box.
- **Your name** - shown here is your Canvas Display Name, which people will see in discussions, messages, and comments. Edit your name if you have a preferred name that you want to use in Canvas. You can also choose to add your pronouns in parentheses.
- **Your title** - We suggest that you add your job title here
- **Your biography** - We suggest pasting in the bio you submitted for the course as part of the onboarding survey. You can find this on the class roster.
- **Link** to your community or organization
- **Link** to your personal Twitter (optional)

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Contact

No registered services, you can add some on the [settings](#) page.

Biography

Organization: CSCCE

Community: CSCCE Community of Practice

About me: Alice is a teaching and learning scholar with a disciplinary background in nutritional biochemistry. She works with the CSCCE Director of Learning to collaboratively design curriculum for trainings, deliver these trainings in the virtual classroom, and build community within cohorts of learners. In her spare time, she enjoys riding bicycles, hiking with her dog, and reading.

Links

[Connect with me on Twitter](#)

[About CSCCE](#)

See the [How do I edit my profile in my user account as a student?](#) Canvas guide for additional information.

B. GENERAL SETTINGS

You can personalize your Canvas experience somewhat by making changes to your settings:

- Select "Account" at the top of the global navigation
- Select "Settings"
- Then, click the "Edit Settings" button

The following settings are available for you to edit:

- **Your Name fields** - If you changed your Display Name in your profile, that will show here. You can also change your Display Name here and update your Full Name if needed.
- **Time zone** - *This is important to set!* Canvas is, by default, set to Eastern Time (US & Canada). Update your time zone to ensure due dates are aligned with your locale.
- **Language** - By default this is set to English (United States), however you can change it to UK, Canada, or Australia which will give you month/day/time formatted for your locale.
- **Contact Methods for Notifications** (on the right-hand side of the page) - By default, this will show the email address with which you logged in.

Note: You will not be able to change your primary email address. If you need assistance with this, please email tech.help@cscce.org.

See the [How do I change the settings in my user account as a student?](#) Canvas guide for additional information.

4. Managing notifications

Canvas can automatically alert you to certain events. To make changes to your Account notifications:

- Select "Account" at the top of the left-side navigation
- Select "Notifications"
- Then, in the dropdown menu, select "Account"

Most notifications are not relevant to CSCCE learners. We suggest you set everything to "Notifications off" except for the following:

- **Announcement:** Notify Immediately
- **Invitation:** Notify Immediately
- **Submission Comment** (for notifications about comments on assignments you submit): Notify Immediately
- **Global Announcements:** Notify Immediately

If you hover over the "Course Activity" listed you will see a brief description for each. See the [How do I manage my Canvas notification settings as a student?](#) Canvas guide for additional information.

That's it – you're good to go!